

Relationship between social context and women's entrepreneurship from the ASOPROMAHER artisanal production association, analyzed using Neutrosophic Cognitive Maps

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Abstract. The study of women's entrepreneurship has been gaining notoriety in the academic community. This research explores the relationship between social context and female entrepreneurship. It is essential to understand the context in which the entrepreneur developed in an environment, to determine how this context affects entrepreneurship due to various factors. This paper aims to describe the influence exerted by the social context on the entrepreneurship of women from the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association in Ecuador. Several aspects, such as family, community, and social networks, are analyzed. It is concluded that the social context significantly influences entrepreneurship and that society is a predominant factor in the female artisan's population that was the basis of the study. It was determined to use the Neutrosophic Cognitive Maps (NCM) because they allow us to represent causal relationships between concepts, in our case, from factors that contextualize female entrepreneurship to female entrepreneurship itself. Furthermore, the explicit inclusion of indeterminacy within this model allows us to adjust this tool to the complexity inherent in this phenomenon, where some relationships are unknown or partially known, and also it is based on subjective assessments.

Keywords: Context, Social context, Entrepreneurship, Female entrepreneurship, Neutrosophic Cognitive Map (NCM).

1 Introduction

Historically, the business and academic worlds have focused on validating male entrepreneurship and studying its characteristics, environment, motivations, and aspirations. However, it was only 35 years ago that the important role of women in the growth of global economies began to be investigated through various studies that unravel the main differences between men and women. As several authors highlight, these studies address differences in management styles, in the results of companies led by people of different genders, among others.

The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, known by its acronym GEM, conducts annual studies at the global, regional, and country levels to measure entrepreneurship. If we delve into the region where Ecuador is located, we can see indicators provided by the GEM that validate the aforementioned importance. In its 2019 report, 49.99% of women entrepreneurs and self-employed individuals in the country have established and functioning businesses. This is even though most of these businesses were

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established out of necessity and without opportunities for short- and medium-term growth.

To analyze this problem, it is necessary to identify its causes. One of them is the lack of understanding about female entrepreneurship. As the reasons for this importance are increasingly being discovered, the rate of female self-employment has been increasing. In a comparative analysis between the 1970s and 1990s, a significant difference can be seen; in 1979, only 3.12% of all economically active women were self-employed; by 1997, this figure had increased to 6.76%. Today, more than 20 years after these studies, some indicators take into account this important group of women entrepreneurs around the world.

This research addresses the issue of the social context in entrepreneurship, which can be defined as the context in which the entrepreneur develops in relation to a particular environment, where there are social influences to which the entrepreneur adapts, and also those factors that influence the individual. Scientists have analyzed various arguments based on historical cases, but a particular understanding is usually unlikely without a general understanding that allows for considering the social context.

The main characteristic of this type of social context is that each person lives in a community that speaks a language and shares certain common problems and concerns. All of this forms the structure of how people define each of their thoughts. In this context, when someone brings together new ideas, it expresses that they are ahead of their time; that is, their proposals do not fit with the general context in which they live. This is what happened to certain women who initiated the feminist movement in the 19th century, as their ideas did not fit the social context in which they lived.

In Santa Elena, there are establishments dedicated to the distribution, purchase, and sale of handicrafts in associations or societies. In this town, there are a considerable number of these types of businesses dedicated to the production sector, where there is currently competition in the local market dedicated to this commercial activity. Therefore, we address the issue of the social context, which requires determining factors such as cultural, family, and social networks.

The influence that social context exerts on women's entrepreneurship is evident in their business activity. Therefore, the justification for this research is based primarily on identifying how the female members of the ASOPROMAHER Association address the social factors of their environment. So, the overall objective of this paper is to describe the influence of the social context on the entrepreneurship of women in the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association in the Santa Elena canton during 2022. This gives us an idea of what is happening today, three years later.

On this topic, there is a background in previous research conducted at the Peninsula of Santa Elena State University in La Libertad. The research was based on inferential statistics, with a randomly selected sample of 281 women from the commune dedicated to entrepreneurship. In addition, this study used a fifteen-question questionnaire to collect information regarding the entrepreneurship program and social development, with Likert-type scales as a measure of evaluation. It was also concluded that women's entrepreneurship is primarily carried out to achieve economic benefits, but it encounters limitations in terms of training to carry out innovative and productive activities.

So, in general, we plan to address the following specific objectives:

- Analyze the causes in the social context and entrepreneurship of women from the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association in the Santa Elena canton.
- Identify social context factors that influence the entrepreneurship of women in the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association in the Santa Elena canton.
- To examine the relationship between social context and entrepreneurship among women in the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association in the Santa Elena canton.

In conducting the proposed research, we faced several challenges; the first one is the presence of uncertainty, indeterminacy, and partial ignorance about the phenomenon under study. Therefore, we decided to use Neutrosophy tools in this study. Neutrosophy is the branch of philosophy dedicated to studying neutralities, where the term neutrality encompasses other concepts, such as indeterminacy, imprecision, lack of information, contradiction, and so on [1]. Due to the subjective nature of perceptions

about female entrepreneurship in a developing country, all these aspects are part of the measurements to be taken into account.

Specifically, we take the Neutrosophic Cognitive Maps (NCM) as the tool that will allow us to carry out the study we propose [2]. NCMs are an extension of Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCM) developed by Kosko, and the latter are a generalization of the Cognitive Maps [3, 4]. All of them consist of a directed graph, where nodes represent concepts and edges represent causal relationships between concepts. Associated with each edge is a weight value that represents the degree to which the source concept causally influences the target concept. The values of these weights determine the type of Cognitive Map. The crisp Cognitive Map contains only weight values equal to either, 0, 1, or -1 to indicate no relationship, direct relationship, or inverse relationship, respectively [5]. FCMs use values between -1 and 1 to qualify the strength of causal relationships between concepts [6, 7]. More recently, NCMs incorporate the value I , which symbolizes indeterminacy [8, 9].

The use of NCMs is a proposal for analyzing causal relationships in social contexts; see some applications in [10-16]. Therefore, we aim to reach valid conclusions about the relationship between social, family, and cultural contexts, among others, and the success of female entrepreneurship among the women who are part of the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association in the Santa Elena canton. To do so, we rely on the criteria of three experts, who identified the essential factors for the study and evaluated the weight of the relationships between every pair of concepts. This research can serve as a basis for similar research within the region or country.

This paper is divided into a Preliminaries section, which explains what Neutrosophic Cognitive Maps are. The Results section contains the variables measured in our study; we designed an NCM and derived a result from it. Section 3 presents the Conclusions.

2 Preliminaries

This section presents the formal mathematical framework for Neutrosophic Cognitive Maps (NCMs) essential to our investigation.

Definition 1 ([1]) Let X denote a universal set. A Neutrosophic Set A in X is defined through three independent membership mappings:

$$T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) : X \rightarrow]^{-0}, 1^{+}[$$

Subject to the constraint:

$$^{-0} \leq \inf T_A(x) + \inf I_A(x) + \inf F_A(x) \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3^{+},$$

Where:

- $T_A(x)$ = truth membership degree,
- $I_A(x)$ = indeterminacy membership degree,
- $F_A(x)$ = falsity membership degree.

Definition 2 ([1]): A *Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set* (SVNS) A subset of X is expressed as:

$$A = \{(x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)) : x \in X\} \quad (1)$$

With $T_A, I_A, F_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$, satisfying:

$$0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$$

A *Single-Valued Neutrosophic Number* simplifies to an ordered triplet (T, I, F) where $T, I, F \in [0, 1]$ and $T + I + F \leq 3$.

Definition 3 ([2, 16, 17]): A *neutrosophic graph* $G = (V, E)$ contains at least one edge $e \in E$ with indeterminate existence, visually represented by dotted lines.

Definition 4 ([2, 16, 17]): A *neutrosophic directed graph* extends Definition 3 with oriented edges, where edge directionality is certain but existence may be indeterminate.

Definition 5 ([2]): A *Neutrosophic Cognitive Map* is a quadruple $NCM = (C, E, W, \Phi)$ where:

- $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}$ are concept nodes,
- $E \subseteq C \times C$ are directed edges,
- $W: E \rightarrow \{-1, 0, 1, I\}$ assigns causal weights,

- $\Phi: C \rightarrow \{0, 1, I\}$ maps node activation states.

Definition 6 ([2]): The *neutrosophic adjacency matrix* M of an NCM is the $k \times k$ matrix where M_{ij} encodes the causal influence of C_i on C_j .

Definition 7 ([2]): A state vector $s \in \{0, 1, I\}^k$ represents the instantaneous activation pattern across all k concepts.

Definition 8 ([2]): An NCM exhibits feedback if its graph contains directed cycles. Such systems are capable of:

- Fixed-point convergence,
- Limit cycle oscillations,
- Chaotic behavior.

Theorem 1 ([2]): For any NCM with feedback, there is a repeated application of the state transition function:

$$s^{(t+1)} = f(W \cdot s^{(t)}).$$

Where f is a threshold function, it will either:

1. Converges to a fixed point s^* where $s^* = f(W \cdot s^*)$, or
2. Enter a periodic limit cycle.

The hidden pattern discovery algorithm proceeds as follows:

1. Initialize s_0 with at least one activated concept,
2. Iteratively compute $s^{(t+1)} = f(W \cdot s^{(t)})$,
3. Fix a threshold τ , and then:
 - Preserves 1 and I values,
 - Converts values $> \tau$ to 1,
 - Converts values $< \tau$ to 0,
 - Maintains I for ambiguous cases.
4. Terminate when:
 - $s^{(t+1)} = s^{(t)}$ (fixed point), or,
 - $s^{(t+1)} \in$ previous states (limit cycle).

The neutrosophic arithmetic is further summarized:

Definition 9 ([2]): The neutrosophic number algebra defines:

1. Addition: $N_1 + N_2 = a_1 + a_1 + (b_1 + b_2)I$,
2. Subtraction: $N_1 - N_2 = a_1 - a_1 + (b_1 - b_2)I$,
3. Multiplication: $N_1 \times N_2 = a_1 a_2 + (a_1 b_2 + b_1 a_2 + b_1 b_2)I$,
4. Division: $\frac{N_1}{N_2} = \frac{a_1 + b_1 I}{a_2 + b_2 I} = \frac{a_1}{a_2} + \frac{a_2 b_1 - a_1 b_2}{a_2(a_2 + b_2)} I$.

Additionally, $I^2 = I$, $0 \cdot I = 0$, $\underbrace{I + I + \dots + I}_{n \text{ times}} = nI$.

3 Results

The research surveyed three experts on entrepreneurship, specifically women's entrepreneurship. They were allowed to analyze the case of the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association in the canton of Santa Elena. They had access to all available information about the association and interviewed the women members. Everyone cooperated, and the first step was to select the concepts relevant to the study.

The experts determined the 10 concepts summarized below to be essential:

C1: Family support to sustain the business.

C2: Promotion of entrepreneurship in the community through fairs, open houses, or municipal invitations.

C3: Inclusion of social networks as part of the enterprise.

C4: Support from digital networks such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram in promoting entrepreneurship.

C5: Support from the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association for the sustainability and growth of the enterprise, as well as training.

C6: Participation in international fairs as support for training and entrepreneurship development.

C7: Knowledge of international markets and the opportunities they provide in the production of handicrafts, such as *toquilla* straw.

C8: The motivation to undertake comes because she feels that she has the skills to do so, and feels the need to improve herself and not simply to look for a job to live on.

C9: There are cultural barriers to being able to practice entrepreneurship properly, for example, machismo.

C10: Successful female entrepreneurship.

Each expert was asked to evaluate the relationship between each of the above concepts to form the matrix M_{ijk} with $i = 1, 2, \dots, 10$; $j = 1, 2, \dots, 10$, where $k = 1, 2, 3$ represents the evaluation of the k th expert. They were asked to use the following scale:

- The concept that is the cause is evaluated as 1 if the relationship between the concepts is direct, and the concept that is the consequence is given a 0. That is, for the k th expert, $M_{ijk} = 1$ if the i th concept is the direct cause of the j th concept (if concept i increases, then concept j increases, and if concept i decreases, then concept j decreases), and therefore $M_{jik} = 0$.
- Contrary to the previous case, the concept that is the cause is evaluated -1 if the relationship is inverse between the concepts (if concept i increases, then concept j decreases, and if concept i decreases, then concept j increases), giving 0 to the concept that is the consequence.
- 0 for M_{ijk} and M_{jik} if there is no relationship between the concepts.
- I for M_{ijk} and for M_{jik} if the relationship between both concepts is unknown or indeterminate.

From the matrices M_{ijk} , a joint matrix denoted by \tilde{M} is formed, such that \tilde{M}_{ij} is equal to the most repeated evaluation among M_{ijk} for all k s.

When for each k , M_{ijk} is different, then \tilde{M}_{ij} is evaluated with I. This is done because it is understood that the experts did not agree among themselves.

The other criterion to follow is that it is enough for one \tilde{M}_{ij} to be evaluated as I to also evaluate \tilde{M}_{ji} as I.

Tables 1, 2, and 3 contain the matrices of all experts' evaluations:

Table 1. Adjacency matrix of the NCM nodes according to expert 1.

Concept	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
C ₁	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
C ₂	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
C ₃	0	0	0	0	I	1	I	0	0	1
C ₄	0	0	1	0	I	I	1	0	0	1
C ₅	1	1	I	I	0	0	0	I	0	1
C ₆	0	1	0	I	1	0	0	I	0	1
C ₇	0	0	I	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
C ₈	1	0	0	0	I	I	0	0	0	1
C ₉	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1
C ₁₀	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2. Adjacency matrix of the NCM nodes according to expert 2.

Concept	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
C ₁	0	0	0	I	I	I	0	0	0	1
C ₂	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
C ₃	0	0	0	0	I	I	I	0	0	1
C ₄	I	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
C ₅	I	1	I	1	0	0	0	I	0	1
C ₆	I	1	I	0	1	0	0	I	0	1
C ₇	0	0	I	0	0	1	0	I	0	1
C ₈	1	0	0	0	I	I	I	0	0	1
C ₉	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1
C ₁₀	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3. Adjacency matrix of the NCM nodes according to expert 3.

Concept	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
C ₁	0	0	0	0	I	0	I	I	0	1
C ₂	0	0	1	1	0	I	1	0	0	1
C ₃	0	0	0	0	0	I	I	I	0	1
C ₄	0	0	1	0	0	I	1	I	0	1
C ₅	I	1	0	1	0	0	I	0	0	1
C ₆	0	I	I	I	1	0	0	0	0	1
C ₇	I	0	I	0	I	1	0	0	0	1
C ₈	I	0	I	I	0	1	0	0	0	1
C ₉	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1
C ₁₀	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4 contains the results of aggregating the criteria of the three experts using the method indicated above:

Table 4. Adjacency matrix of the NCM nodes according to the criteria of all experts.

Concept	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
C ₁	0	0	0	0	I	0	0	0	0	1
C ₂	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
C ₃	0	0	0	0	I	I	I	0	0	1
C ₄	0	0	1	0	0	I	1	0	0	1
C ₅	I	1	I	1	0	0	0	I	0	1
C ₆	0	1	I	I	1	0	0	I	0	1
C ₇	0	0	I	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
C ₈	1	0	0	0	I	I	0	0	0	1
C ₉	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1
C ₁₀	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 1 contains the NCM graph from Table 4.

Figure 1. Pictorial representation of the NCM. Green lines represent direct causality, red lines represent indirect causality, and blue lines represent indeterminacy.

By applying the Method for Determining Hidden Patterns, we analyzed the possible combinations of 10-component vectors with zero (deactivated) and one (activated) values. From these, we eliminated the degenerate case with all null values, as well as the cases in which C_{10} is activated, since we needed to determine under what conditions this node, the target of this investigation, is activated. In 99.2172% of the combinations, an indeterminate result was obtained for C_{10} , while in the remaining cases (4 in total, or 0.7828%), C_{10} was activated with a value of 1. Let us analyze the cases in detail:

Case 1. $X_0 = (1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0)$, and then we have:

It is obtained $X_0 M = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 8)$ and it becomes into:

$X_1 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1)$,

Then, $X_1 M = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 8)$ which becomes:

$X_2 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1)$,

And then $X_1 = X_2$.

Case 2. $X_0 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0)$ and following the method we have:

$X_0 M = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 8)$ which becomes:

$X_1 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1)$,

$X_1 M = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 8)$ which becomes:

$X_2 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1)$,

And then $X_1 = X_2$.

Case 3. $X_0 = (1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0)$ with the sequence:

$X_0 M = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 6)$,

$X_1 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$,

$X_1 M = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 7)$, and

$X_2 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$,

And then $X_1 = X_2$.

Case 4. $X_0 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0)$ and then,

$X_0 M = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 7)$,

$X_1 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$,

$X_1 M = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 7)$, and

$X_2 = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$,

And then $X_1 = X_2$.

These results indicate that concepts C_1 , C_3 , C_4 , C_5 , C_6 , C_7 , and C_8 are essential for successful female entrepreneurship. Concept C_2 (Promotion at festivals, fairs, and others) will be activated if the previous

concepts are activated. Finally, C_9 is not essential for successful female entrepreneurship.

4. Conclusion

In the research conducted on the social context and female entrepreneurship, we can confirm that the former influences the latter. Three experts selected the factors that influence the effective implementation of female entrepreneurship. This knowledge was represented with the help of Neutrosophic Cognitive Maps, specifically the Simple Neutrosophic Cognitive Maps, and the Method for Determining the Hidden Patterns was applied. In this way, causal relationships between concepts are taken into account, and conclusions can be drawn by simulating the dynamic evolution of these relationships. As a result, it was concluded that the essential aspects for a successful business are:

- Family support to sustain the business.
- Inclusion of social networks as part of entrepreneurship.
- Support of digital networks in promoting entrepreneurship.
- Support from the ASOPROMAHER Artisanal Production Association for the sustainability and growth of the business, as well as training.
- Participation in international fairs to support training and entrepreneurial development.
- Knowledge of international markets and the opportunities they offer in the production of handicrafts, such as *toquilla* straw.
- The motivation to start a business comes from feeling that women have the skills to do so, from the need to improve themselves, and not from simply looking for a job to subsist.

On the other hand, currently, a factor such as “the existence of cultural barriers to successful entrepreneurship, such as sexism,” even if present, is not an obstacle to achieving the proposed objective. While “promoting entrepreneurship in the community through fairs, open houses, or municipal invitations” is a consequence of the other factors.

Given all this knowledge, we propose to the decision-makers and entrepreneurial women in general of this artisanal association that they foster the aforementioned positive factors that will guarantee their business success.

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